

PHILOSOPHY OF HEALTH IN ZOROASTRIAN DOCTRINE

RADJABOV OTABEK ATOEVICH

Teacher of the Bukhara State Medical Institute Uzbekistan, Bukhara

Abstract:

In this article, the philosophy of Health in the doctrine of Zoroastrianism is widely covered. The Zoroastrian doctrine encourages its followers to take care of the body and maintain its integrity. It emphasizes the importance of a healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition, physical activity and adherence to hygiene rules. In Zoroastrian philosophy of Health, there is a belief that a healthy body promotes healthy mind and spirit.

Keywords: *Zoroastrianism, philosophy of health, healthy lifestyle, Avesto.*

Introduction

The highly developed Zoroastrian culture and the harmonization of Islam served as the basis for the unique development of ideas about health, unlike others. In the 9th-8th centuries BC, a new and very strong doctrine appeared in Central Asia about the structure of the world and the role of man in it, which did not correspond to previous views. The religious and philosophical problems created by him are still being discussed to this day in the works of various researchers, in addition to being a doctrine that can resist the polytheism and extravagance that has formed in the territory, the pollution of the environment and the extermination of living animals that have played an important role in human life. Avesto medicine, which is directly involved in our research, in other words, the philosophy of Health in Zoroastrianism has become an integral part of world civilization, in addition to serving humanity for more than 2702 years in a historical period [1]. The "Avesto", which continues to be a link in the name of the Prophet Zarathustra, is considered not only a complex of religious beliefs, but also a great artistic-philosophical monument. For Zoroastrian ancestors were originally from Khwarezm, and he was born and brought up in this paradise land, where he learned science, where he is a captive, inspired by his philosophical ideas. Zarathustra is the one payrambari, the first poet and philosopher of the world [2]. The "Avesto" embodied the ancient medical and purity views of our ancestors. It is known that Alexander Macedonsky, after conquering Iran, Movarounnahr, sent the most perfect, rare copy of the "Avesto" to Ella, tarzhima the Greek parts of history, mathematics, astronomy, geography, medicine and burned the original. The avestoshunos share in the Kohna copy of the work that the text of the medicine man's oath was a snake bite that was pouring poison on the Jom [3, 4]. The Hippocratic Oath, the so-called Doctor's

oath, the symbol of Medicine, also came out of our original self. So, a comprehensive study of the views on medicine in this ancient venture of spirituality is a cone of benefit both for the history of our science and for our current medicine [5].

In Zoroastrian traditions, body health is considered important, since it is a means of achieving mental integrity. Zoroastrianism encourages its followers to take care of the body and maintain its integrity. It emphasizes the importance of a healthy lifestyle, proper nutrition, physical activity and adherence to hygiene rules [6, 7]. There is a belief in Zoroastrian philosophy of Health that a healthy body promotes common sense and spirit.

Zoroastrians believe that the health of the mind is also an important aspect of the philosophy of general health. Zoroastrianism encourages people to develop intelligence, knowledge and wisdom. Reason is considered a tool that helps a person make the right decisions and act in accordance with his spiritual beliefs. Mental health also occupies a central place in Zoroastrian religion [8]. Zoroastrian philosophy of Health emphasizes the importance of striving for mental maturity, spiritual maturity. Zoroastrians seek to strengthen their spirits and achieve harmony with the cosmic order through faith, prayer, meditation and spiritual practices.

The philosophy of Health in the doctrine of Zoroastrianism is based on the understanding of man as a harmonious being composed of body, mind and soul. Zoroastrian philosophy of Health seeks to achieve balance and harmony between these three aspects of human nature.

The general philosophy of Health in the doctrine of Zoroastrianism involves taking care of the body, developing the mind and developing the soul. These three aspects are seen as interconnected and integral parts of human life. Zoroastrianism's philosophy of Health aims to achieve harmony between these aspects and the overall well-being of the individual.

Ushta is a state of being when the body, mind and spirit are in a state of well-being and tranquility (armaiti). The purpose of life in Zoroastrianism is to achieve the goal. A healthy mind (mainyu) and mind (man) in a healthy body (tan) — in other words, a state of spiritual, mental and physical well-being — allows a person to lead an active, meaningful and fulfilling life and realize his hwarana - his highest vocation and full potential. Therefore, a person should actively build and maintain well-being. The lack of well-being can interrupt this search or state of being. Zoroastrians have been developing approaches to healing and recovery for centuries.

Although physical health is important for a person to lead a full and productive life, achieving intelligence does not depend on perfect health when such an ideal is impossible. Even when a person is approaching the end of his physical life, the goal of Zoroastrianism is to approach such an opportunity in spiritual health and comfort — calmness and equanimity.

In Zoroastrianism, being has spiritual (mainyu) and material/physical (gaeta) aspects. Therefore, in order for well-being or healing to be complete and effective, both aspects must be taken into account. In addition, because spiritual existence fills the physical, spiritual well-being or healing enables the physical body to support or heal itself.

Healing from the point of view of Zoroastrianism goes beyond the search for a physical cure for a certain disease or symptom. Healing, the application of external help or intervention, helps healing happen from within. Healing can provide an environment for healing. Healing occurs when the body uses its own resources to restore a person to a state that preceded the onset of the disease.

If a disease occurs, the human body naturally seeks to restore health through healing. If there is a lack of mental well-being, a person needs to dig deeper and direct their spiritual abilities to healing. Physical (including mental) and spiritual healing are interrelated, and Zoroastrian healing approaches help a person's natural healing abilities as an individual and as a member of a community.

An example of the Zoroastrian approach to holistic health promotion and healing is the discipline of chaos. Chaos uses the natural remedies provided by nature, while invoking the spiritual healing provided by the mantra - verses contained in the Zoroastrian scriptures. The approach is aimed at establishing harmony and eliminating the imbalance between the physical and spiritual aspects of a person.

In the conclusion siphon, it can be said that the philosophy of Health in the doctrine of Zoroastrianism is based on the understanding of man as a harmonious being composed of body, mind and soul. Zoroastrian philosophy of Health seeks to achieve balance and harmony between these three aspects of human nature. In Zoroastrian traditions, body health is considered important, since it is a means of achieving mental integrity.

REFERENCE

1. Науменко О. А. Некоторые философские аспекты правовых, религиозных и нравственных идей в учении зороастризма // Материалы IV Международной научной конференции "Донецкие чтения: образование, наука, инновации, культура и вызовы современности": статья в сборнике трудов конференции. — 2019. — 31 октября (т. 5). — С. 88—91.
2. Рахимов С. Х. Философско-эстетические идеи зороастризма. Автореферат диссертации на соискание учёной степени доктора философских наук. — Душанбе: Институт философии Академии наук Республики Таджикистан, 2007. — С. 16.
3. Нуруллаева Ш. К. Эгамберганова М. Д. Вопросы семьи и брака в "Авесте" // Общественные науки : электронный научный журнал. — 2016. — № 6(24). Давлатова Е. В. Мифология зороастризма и становление христианства // Учёные записки УО ВГУ им. П.М. Машерова : журнал. — 2010. — Т. 10. — С. 142—148. — ISSN = 2075-1613 issn = 2075-1613.
4. Авеста: Избранные гимны / Перевод И.М. Стеблин-Каменского. — М.: Дружба народов, 1993. — 207 с. — ISBN 5-285-00127-7.
5. Стеблин-Каменский И. М. Предисловие // Авеста: Избранные гимны : книга. — 1993. — С. 3—12.
6. Желтова Е. В. Античная традиция о персидских магах. — СПб.: Издательство Санкт-Петербургского университета, 2011. — С. 68. — ISBN 978-5-288-05202-6..
7. Гафуров Б. Г. Таджики: древнейшая, древняя и средневековая история. Кн. 1. — Душанбе: Ирфон, 1989. — С. 59.
8. Холикзода А.Г. Авеста как основной источник зороастрийского права // Юридическая наука: история и современность : журнал. — 2018. — № 12. — С. 172—184.